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Deliverable 10.2

Governance Model of the legal entity

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Abstract

This report outlines the ECHOES proposal for a distributed, multi-level, collaborative governance model for the future Cultural Heritage Cloud legal entity. Based on a comprehensive benchmarking of legal options and governance models from comparable European initiatives, it recommends an institutionalisation process as a two-step strategy that involves creating a temporary non-profit association before creating a European Digital Infrastructure Consortium (EDIC).

This recommendation is based on a benchmarking exercise that illustrates the necessity of having a first agile legal entity during the project funding phase to prepare the creation of a more complex and long-term governance structure, such as an EDIC. After comparing the different legal options, this report recommends EDICs as the best-suited legal option to ensure the participation of different types of stakeholders, such as Member States, European networks and initiatives, cultural heritage institutions, and private companies.

This report also outlines the main features of the Cloud technical governance within these phases and uses a thematic focus on combating illicit trafficking in cultural goods to illustrate how the future Cloud governance can be adapted to an existing complex, multi-actor governance framework in the field of cultural heritage.

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List of abbreviations

AAI	Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AISBL	Association Internationale Sans But Lucratif
ALT-EDIC	Alliance for Language Technologies EDIC
API	Application Programming Interface
BCE	Banque Carrefour des Entreprises
CAB	Community Advisory Board
CDR	Call Data Records
CIDOC CRM	International Committee for Documentation Conceptual Reference Model
DDPP	Digital Decade Policy Programme
DG DIGIT	Directorate-General for Informatics
DG RTD	Directorate-General for Research and Innovation
ECCCH	European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage
ECG	Export Cultural Goods
EDIC	European Digital Infrastructure Consortium
IMPACT	European Multidisciplinary Platform Against Criminal Threats
ENSP	École Nationale Supérieure de la Police
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERA	European Research Area
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
E-RIHS	European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GA	General Assembly
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HDTO	Heritage Digital Twin Ontology
ICG	Import Cultural Goods

KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LEA	Law Enforcement Agency
OCBC	Office Central de lutte contre le trafic de Biens Culturels
OCRA	Online Conservation Restoration Annotator
OSINT	Open Source Intelligence
RCH	Resilient Cultural Heritage
RTI	Reflectance Transformation Imaging
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SNA	Social Network Analysis
SOC	Strategic Orientation Committee
SRIA	Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda
SUE	Sistema Unico di Esportazione
TCA	Trade and Cooperation Agreement
TCG	Trafficking of Cultural Goods
TechOp	Technical Operations
TPC	Comando Tutela Patrimonio Culturale
UKRI	United Kingdom Research and Innovation
WCO	World Customs Organisation

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Introduction

The Cultural Heritage Cloud is a comprehensive European initiative that aims to bring together a wide range of stakeholders, from diverse institutions and backgrounds, around collaborative Digital Commons. Its vision relies on the integration of distributed technical resources, on the active participation of Cultural Heritage and Digital communities and actors, and on long-term commitments to open science within the field. The development of the Cloud is supported by significant investment from the European Union and benefits from collaborations with other relevant initiatives and actors at the European, regional, national, and local levels.

As a platform project, ECHOES is preparing the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH), also known as the Cultural Heritage Cloud, to become a self-governed and legal entity after the current Horizon Europe funding period, which ends in 2029. This report describes the strategy and next steps to reach this objective.

By providing a legal pathway to a sustainable entity and the design of the future cloud governance, it prepares the ground for the discussion and negotiation phase of the detailed decision-making mechanisms of the legal entity, which will start in June 2026. As a public document, this deliverable is primarily addressed to current or potential stakeholders of the future Cloud legal entity. It may also serve as a reference for other European initiatives exploring comparable legal frameworks for large-scale collaboration.

The Cultural Heritage Cloud is a distributed technical infrastructure with a federated community of cultural heritage professionals, researchers, and digital experts. As such, it requires an equally distributed and multi-level governance framework. The Cultural Heritage Cloud institutionalisation process must take this complexity into account.

Based on a combination of desktop and legal research and expert interviews (which are further described in an ancillary document),¹ this deliverable proposes a staged institutionalisation process that starts with the creation of a nonprofit association (AISBL) in the short-term and continues with the establishment of a European Digital Infrastructure Consortium (EDIC) in the longer-term. This strategy is supported by recommended governance bodies and technical governance processes, which will be used as a starting point for discussion and negotiation with stakeholders to discuss detailed decision-making processes and sustainability options. This negotiation phase starts in June 2026.

¹ Borin, E., Cringoli, G., Giodino, D., Puhr, A. (2026) *A Framework Analysis of European Legal Entities: Complementary Paper of Deliverable 10.2 "Governance Model of the legal entity"*.

To illustrate how the Cultural Heritage Cloud governance can gradually be adapted to address the needs and realities of an existing complex, multi-actor field of activity, this report concludes with a thematic focus on recommendations for including the fight against illicit trafficking in cultural goods into the Cloud.

1 A complex governance landscape with several legal options

1.1 The legal and policy landscape of Digital Cultural Heritage

The Cultural Heritage Cloud operates within a complex European legal and policy framework shaping digital services, data governance, interoperability, and collaboration. Key EU regulations and initiatives define requirements for data protection, innovation, trust, and cross-border cooperation. Interactions with Common European Data Spaces and, where relevant, the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), help align digital and research infrastructures.

The EU has developed a rights-based digital governance framework grounded in principles such as privacy, non-discrimination, and user protection, notably reflected in the European Declaration on Digital Rights and Principles and the Digital Decade Policy Programme 2030. Together, these initiatives support the EU objective of a human-centred and sovereign digital society.

Within this framework, the European data strategy ecosystem aims to create a Single Market for Data through harmonised rules on access, reuse, interoperability, and trust. Common European Data Spaces provide secure and interoperable environments for data sharing across sectors, including health, mobility, public administration, and research. Research infrastructures such as EOSC complement this architecture by enabling federated access to scientific data and supporting cross-disciplinary collaboration.

Overall, this legal and policy framework seeks to reconcile fundamental rights, technological sovereignty, and economic competitiveness while providing the conditions for secure and interoperable cross-border flows of data and services. The main European norms and regulations that will shape the functioning of the Cultural Heritage Cloud Governance are:

Name	Type	Description	Impact on the ECCCH Governance
General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)	Regulation (EU) 2016/679	The EU’s core data-protection framework. It harmonises data-protection rules across the EU and EEA while strengthening individuals’ control over personal data.	The Cloud will collect some personal data over its users. The governance model should enable GDPR compliance across all distributed services and activities.
Digital Service Act (DSA)	Regulation (EU) 2022/2065	Common EU framework for safer and more transparent online services. It imposes obligations on intermediaries and online platforms regarding illegal content, transparency, accountability, and user protection.	The Cloud will host “content”. The governance model should enable DSA compliance in collaboration with its data and service providers.
EU Artificial Intelligence Act (AI Act)	Regulation (EU) 2024/1689	The first comprehensive EU framework regulating AI systems. It adopts a risk-based approach aimed at ensuring AI systems are safe, transparent, traceable, and compliant with fundamental rights.	Some Cloud services will fall under the AI Act. The Cloud governance must be able to adapt to an evolving complex legal and ethical environment.
Open Data and Re-use of Public Sector Information Directive	Directive (EU) 2019/1024	It establishes harmonised rules for the reuse of public-sector and publicly funded research data. It promotes an “open by default” approach requiring	A significant part of the data accessed, used or reused on the Cloud will fall within the scope of this directive. The Cloud governance must help its

data to be accessible, machine-readable, and reusable.

members comply with this directive, including its technical recommendations.

Interoperable Europe Act	Regulation (EU) 2024/903	A binding framework to strengthen interoperability among EU public administrations and digital systems. Its objective is to enable seamless cross-border digital public services by 2030.	While it does not directly apply to the Cloud governance, this regulation will apply to several of its members. The Cloud will explore the solutions recommended by the Interoperable Europe Portal
The European Interoperability Framework (EIF)	European Framework	A recommended European interoperability framework that provides principles, interoperability layers, integration components and technical recommendations. A new version is expected soon.	Following the example of EOOSC, the Cloud governance should provide a platform of interoperability governance and organisational interoperability for its members.
Digital Decade Policy Programme 2030	European Programme	Sets a clear direction for Europe’s digital transformation, aiming for secure, interoperable, and human-centred digital infrastructures and services. It contributes to achieving the Single Market for Data across Member States.	The Cloud governance should, in collaboration of the Data Space for Cultural Heritage, help its member reach the Digital Decade Policy objectives. A more detailed analysis of these objectives is available in Annex 2 .

Table 1: Summary of key European legislation and programmes and their impact on the Cloud governance design

1.2 The existing legal options for the Cloud legal entity

Several legal options are both suitable and available for establishing the Cultural Heritage Cloud as a legal entity while meeting the previously defined Cloud governance requirements.² These include the AISBL and comparable national association models, as well as the ERIC and EDIC frameworks.

To evaluate these options comprehensively and determine which legal entity is best suited to the future ECCCH ecosystem, a twofold approach was adopted: a systematic desktop research, complemented by qualitative expert interviews.

The desktop research aimed to provide an initial set of resources and information about the current European and national legal landscapes. A list of legal entities of interest was first established and refined throughout the research process. Building upon the work carried out within E-RIHS, the research gathered information about the creation process and the maintenance of a panel of legal entities, ranging from national options to European entities, including EDICs. Each legal entity was first examined individually, with findings organised according to sections defined beforehand and applied consistently across all considered options. Each section dedicated to a specific framework concludes with a summary insert outlining its main advantages and disadvantages for the Cloud.

In the next step, qualitative expert interviews were held to deepen the analysis and expand on the results of the desktop research by consulting representatives of selected organisations corresponding to the entity models under study. From December 2025 to February 2026, 15 experts (partly ECHOES partners) across the four entity models ERIC, EDIC, AISBL under Belgian law, and Foundation/Association under Dutch law were interviewed by the ECHOES Consortium. Based on a structured template, the interviews addressed areas that required further understanding and gathered individual expert insights, particularly regarding the processes involved in establishing a legal entity, rather than focusing solely on its final form.

The questions covered a wide range of topics, including administrative and operational requirements, governance and business models, as well as cooperation frameworks. The full analysis of the expert interviews and the respective entity models is provided in the Complementary Paper “A Framework Analysis of European Legal Entities” (Borin, Cringoli, Giordino & Pühr 2026). The transversal findings were consolidated in a master table (pp.21-22).

² Pollé, A., et al. (2025) *ECHOES Founding principles of the Cloud Governance (D10.2)*.

Association Internationale Sans But Lucratif (AISBL)

The *Association Internationale Sans But Lucratif* (AISBL) is a Belgian legal form established under the law of 27 June 1921 and revised in 2002, specifically designed for organisations with international, non-economic objectives. Its key strength lies in its capacity to bring together highly diverse partners: public authorities and private actors, individuals and organisations, from Europe and beyond. As it remains entirely governed by Belgian national law, its registered office must be located on Belgian territory.

Creation and legal establishment

Establishing an AISBL requires a formal application to the Federal Public Service of Justice, including proposed statutes and a notarised authentic act. Crucially, the AISBL only acquires legal personality upon royal authorisation granted by the Minister of Justice, after which its existence is formalised through publication in the *Moniteur belge*. This authorisation must be renewed whenever the association modifies its objectives or activities. Following authorisation, the AISBL must register in the Banque Carrefour des Entreprises (BCE) and file the relevant documents with the competent Trade Court. Despite the multiple steps involved, the process is generally completed within a matter of weeks.

Governance and internal structure

The internal organisation of an AISBL is based on a mandatory dual governance structure. It must include an executive organ (*organe général de direction*), which manages the association's strategic orientation, and an administrative organ (*organe d'administration*), which oversees day-to-day management and operational responsibilities. The statutes of the association describe in detail how the General Assembly is convened, how decisions are taken, how voting procedures are structured, and how the internal balance of power is maintained. This statutory framework ensures stability and clarity in the governance of the organisation while allowing for the international participation that the AISBL form was designed to accommodate.

Financial, accounting and tax requirements

Annual accounts must be approved by the General Assembly and filed with the Trade Court. If the AISBL conducts regular economic activities independently and for payment, VAT registration and periodic declarations are required.

Limited VAT exemptions exist for member-only services or activities of a political, charitable, or civic nature, but these remain narrower than in many other national systems, representing a meaningful constraint for organisations with diverse revenue streams.

Participation in European research programmes

AISBLs are fully eligible for European funding programmes. Under Horizon 2020, they qualify under Article 9(3)(d) of the Rules of Participation, allowing them to apply for and receive grants provided they meet the competence, operational, and thematic requirements of each call.

Advantages and challenges for the Cultural Heritage Cloud

For a structure such as the Culture Heritage Cloud, the AISBL model offers notable advantages. It can be established relatively quickly and has the distinctive capacity to host a wide diversity of members from various countries and sectors. These characteristics make it particularly suitable for international cooperation initiatives.

However, its adoption also entails some challenges. Despite the relatively short timeframe, the administrative process is technically complex and requires close coordination among founders. Additionally, participating States must agree to engage in a legal entity governed entirely by Belgian law, which may raise concerns or require negotiations. Finally, the restrictive nature of Belgian VAT exemptions can limit the financial flexibility of the organisation.

In line with these findings, several interviewees acknowledged the AISBL as a viable and highly flexible legal form for European networks and coordination structures, while also emphasising that it does not necessarily constitute an optimal long-term solution for ECHOES due to unresolved issues related to financial sustainability, cross-border staffing, and recurring compliance costs. (Borin, Cringoli, Giordino & Pühr 2026)

Other national non-profit associations

In order to situate the AISBL within the wider landscape of nonprofit legal forms, here are several examples of comparable national associations.

France – Association Loi 1901

Highly flexible and administratively light, with straightforward governance around a General Assembly and board. International reach is achievable in practice but is not intrinsic to the legal design, which remains rooted in French administrative tradition.

Germany – eingetragener Verein (e.V.)

Legally robust, transparent, and well-governed, offering strong legal personality and institutional credibility. International activities are possible but emerge as an extension of purpose rather than a founding rationale, and the model does not specifically facilitate cross-border institutional cooperation.

Italy – Associazione Riconosciuta / Non Riconosciuta

Two variants differing in formality and liability protection. Recognised status offers stronger legal standing but is time-consuming to obtain due to ministerial oversight. Neither form was conceived for European-level coordination or multinational governance.

Spain – Asociación sin Ánimo de Lucro

Straightforward to establish and well-suited to cultural and scientific initiatives. International engagement depends on internal statutes rather than legal design, making it practical for domestic work with international reach but not for pan-European coordination.

Austria – Verein

Simple, efficient, and popular among NGOs and international networks for its neutrality and ease of use. International membership capacity is a functional feature rather than a legally embedded purpose, and it lacks the explicit multinational mission of the AISBL.

Netherlands – Vereniging

Easy to establish, member-driven, and administratively light. Functional for international activities but designed primarily for national purposes, with governance and reporting obligations firmly grounded in Dutch law.

In the interviews, experts on Association / Foundation models highlighted recurring challenges related to dependence on EU and project-based funding, limited internal administrative capacity, and the legal and administrative complexity of cross-border employment. The full outcomes of the interview exploitations are provided in the Complementary Paper “A Framework Analysis of European Legal Entities” (Borin, Cringoli, Giordino & Pühr 2026).

European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC)

General presentation

The ERIC is a legal framework established by Council Regulation (EC) No 723/2009 of 25 June 2009, designed to facilitate the creation and long-term operation of research infrastructures of European interest. It provides stable, legally secure and flexible structures for large-scale, cross-border research initiatives, playing a key role in strengthening the European Research Area (ERA). An ERIC operates primarily on a non-economic basis but may undertake limited ancillary economic activities. Its statutory seat must be located within the EU, and it falls under the jurisdiction of the Court of Justice of the European Union. Membership is open to EU Member States, associated countries, third countries and intergovernmental organisations, with a minimum of three state members including at least one EU Member State. The European Commission is explicitly excluded from membership.

Purpose and European added value

To qualify, an ERIC must constitute a genuine European joint venture, be necessary for the implementation of research programmes, and demonstrate tangible added value for Europe through scientific and technological progress. Open access for the European research community is a fundamental principle, alongside promotion of researcher mobility and active dissemination and reuse of research results. Since 2009, twenty-six ERICs have been established across domains, including social sciences, humanities, environmental research, life sciences, physics and cultural heritage.

Creation process and duration

The creation of an ERIC follows a two-step process, typically taking around two years. The first phase verifies compliance with the ERIC Regulation, including a declaration by the host state recognising the ERIC as an international body for VAT and excise duty purposes. The second phase consists of a formal application to the European Commission, jointly signed by all prospective members, including proposed statutes, a technical and scientific description of the infrastructure, member declarations recognising legal personality, and agreements on applicable tax exemptions. The Commission consults the ERIC Committee before publishing its decision in the Official Journal of the EU. Timelines vary depending on national administrative contexts.

Governance and organisational models

Each ERIC must include at least two mandatory governance bodies: an Assembly of Members as the supreme decision-making authority, and a Director or Board of Directors responsible for management and legal representation. Beyond these, ERICs enjoy significant organisational flexibility. In practice, all existing ERICs have established independent scientific advisory bodies. Most operate as distributed infrastructures, combining a central coordination hub with nationally organised nodes, balancing European coordination with national expertise.

Financial framework and participation in EU programmes

ERICs are primarily funded through member contributions, ensuring shared responsibility and long-term sustainability. As entities established under Union law, they are fully eligible for EU funding and can be identified as direct participants in grant agreements, with contributing members recognised as linked third parties. A significant advantage is eligibility for VAT and excise duty exemptions for non-economic activities, though practical application remains complex, particularly for in-kind contributions and cross-border transactions.

Overall assessment

The ERIC framework is a robust and well-established instrument for European research infrastructure. Its key strengths include operation under EU law, broad legal capacity across Member States, governance flexibility, and meaningful fiscal advantages. Its main challenges include high requirements to gain political commitment from Member States, the lack of harmonisation of national employment rules, constraints on economic activities, difficulties applying VAT exemptions to in-kind contributions, and a lengthy creation process. Despite these limitations, the ERIC has become a cornerstone of European research governance and a reference model for long-term transnational scientific cooperation.

Aligned with this assessment, the interviewees portray this model as a robust and credible long-term legal framework for mature distributed research infrastructures, provided that adequate political support, administrative capacity, and transitional funding are available early on, while also pointing to its complex governance structure and persistent reliance on hybrid funding sources. (Borin, Cringoli, Giordino & Pühr 2026)

European Digital Infrastructure Consortium (EDIC)

General presentation

The EDIC is a legal and organisational instrument introduced by Decision (EU) 2022/2481 of 14 December 2022, establishing the Digital Decade Policy Programme (DDPP) 2030, with its legal framework set out in Articles 13 to 23 of that Decision. EDICs were designed to cover a broader scope of activities, extending beyond research to support large-scale, multi-country digital infrastructure projects contributing to Europe's digital transformation. This includes digital capacities, data infrastructures, artificial intelligence, virtual worlds, blockchain-based public services, and smart city systems.

EDICs explicitly encourage collaboration between public authorities, private entities, industry stakeholders and end users. Participation is open to Member States, and can be open to other entities, including a limited selection of third countries, international organisations of European interest, and public and private entities, according to conditions set in the statutes and compliance with EU legal and financial frameworks. Sustainability, long-term viability and reuse of digital assets are core principles of the model. Member States nonetheless retain strong governance control, with strategic authority firmly anchored in public authorities.

Creation process and duration

The creation of an EDIC follows a two-step procedure. Member States first submit a formal application to the European Commission, including proposed statutes, a technical description of the infrastructure, and a declaration from the host Member State regarding international body recognition. The Commission then assesses the application in consultation with the Digital Decade Policy Programme Committee and decides on approval. A minimum of three Member States is required. EDICs can typically be established within six months of the formal request.

Governance structure and internal organisation

Each EDIC must include two mandatory governance bodies: an Assembly of Members holding decision-making authority, and a Director appointed by the Assembly as the executive body and legal representative. The Assembly includes both members and the European Commission, though the Commission generally holds no voting rights unless a centrally managed Union programme provides financial contributions, in which case it gains veto rights. Voting rights are reserved for Member States that provide financial or in-kind contributions, and private or public entities may not outvote Member States, regardless of their level of contribution, thereby preserving public control.

Beyond these mandatory bodies, EDICs enjoy substantial flexibility to establish additional committees, advisory bodies, or implementing structures through their statutes.

Financial framework and participation in EU programmes

EDICs are primarily financed through member contributions, whether financial or in-kind, complemented by EU grants. They are fully eligible for programmes such as Horizon Europe, the Digital Europe Programme, and the Connecting Europe Facility. Where the host Member State recognises the EDIC as an international organisation, VAT and excise duty exemptions may apply for goods and services, representing a significant advantage for large-scale digital infrastructure investments.

Overall assessment: advantages and challenges

For initiatives like the Cultural Heritage Cloud, the EDIC offers extensive legal capacity across EU Member States, a relatively rapid creation process, governance flexibility, support for diverse actor collaboration, eligibility for economic activities linked to digital services, and potential VAT exemptions. Key challenges include limited practical guidance on human resources rules, the political commitment and coordination required from Member States, and the current exclusion of third countries not formally associated with a directly managed Union digital programme.

Existing governance models of EDICs

Three existing EDICs illustrate the framework's adaptability. ALT-EDIC, hosted by France and seated in Villers-Cotterêts, focuses on European language data and AI language technologies, with governance centred on an Assembly of Members supported by a Strategic Orientation Committee and multiple consultative bodies. Its statutes explicitly regulate staff employment under EU and national law. LDT CitiVERSE EDIC, created on 1 February 2024 and hosted by Spain in Valencia, aims to interconnect local digital twins across Europe for urban planning and citizen engagement, currently involving fourteen Member States. EUROPEUM-EDIC, established on 21 May 2024 and hosted by Belgium, builds on the European Blockchain Services Infrastructure to deliver cross-border public services, governed by an Assembly of Members supported by a Strategic Orientation Board and an EU Bodies Advisory Committee.

The challenge of UK participation in EDICs

The United Kingdom is a major contributor to the ECHOES project through UKRI-funded participation and involvement of key institutions such as the Archaeology Data Service and the National Gallery.

It plays a significant role in the development of the Cultural Heritage Cloud through the participation of British institutions in other ECCCH-funded projects as well.

The United Kingdom is not part of the EU Digital Decade Programme, and as such, is not subject to its governance mechanisms. Nevertheless, it remains structurally connected to the EU digital regulatory space through market access constraints, regulatory spillovers, and increasing institutional cooperation. It also participates in several ERICs, and in the cultural heritage sector it is a founding member of E-RIHS.

Across the four pillars of the Digital Decade, there is clear and substantive convergence between the UK and EU policy objectives (see [Annex 2](#)), but persistent divergence in legal form and approaches, as visible in the UK 2025 Modern Industrial Strategy and sector-specific legislation.

Since late 2024, this divergence has been partially offset by renewed alignment dynamics, particularly in AI and cybersecurity, reinforced by the extraterritorial application of EU law (notably the AI Act), which directly affects UK firms operating in the EU market. This functional convergence is increasingly embedded in structured cooperation. Since the May 2025 UK–EU summit, institutional exchanges have intensified, including meetings of the Withdrawal Agreement Joint Committee and TCA Partnership Council in February 2026 on digital regulation, ongoing cyber dialogues, and discussions on digital finance in the March 2026 Financial Regulatory Forum.

In parallel, several legal and policy routes could facilitate UK involvement in the European Digital Infrastructure Consortium (EDIC) for the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage.

The UK could participate as a non-state member within EDIC governance structures through its research organisations, and rely on the Horizon Europe association to satisfy eligibility requirements for participation in directly managed Union programmes. In addition, the EDIC’s flexible statutory design, modelled on the ERIC framework and already open in practice to strategic partnerships with third countries, provides further governance space for UK inclusion over time.

Consistent with the overall assessment of EDICs, the experts in the interviews identify the model as promising for politically backed, mission-driven European infrastructures, particularly in contexts where close coordination between Member States and the industry is essential, as elaborated in the Complementary Paper “A Framework Analysis of European Legal Entities” (Borin, Cringoli, Giordino & Pühr 2026).

Transversal summary of interviews exploitation

Legal form	Main implementation or operational challenges	Governance and funding implications
AISBL	<p>The main difficulties concerned Belgian administrative procedures, banking requirements, language barriers, notarial obligations, transparency and anti-money-laundering requirements, and the need for local legal or administrative support. Some organisations found the set-up manageable and fast, while others experienced significant operational friction, especially when they lacked staff or presence in Belgium.</p>	<p>AISBLs allow flexible governance structures, including General Assemblies, boards, working groups, scientific or advisory committees and member-based representation. Funding models vary widely: some depend heavily on membership fees, others on EU projects, services, inventories, or mixed public-private sources. Project dependency was often seen as unstable, and HR or employment arrangements across countries were identified as a recurring issue.</p>
Foundations/Associations under Dutch law	<p>Implementation was generally less politically complex than ERIC or EDIC processes, but challenges included choosing the most appropriate national legal framework, negotiating differentiated financial contributions, managing dependency on another organisation, and dealing with limited capacity to generate income directly from content or activities.</p>	<p>These structures can support transparent governance, independent boards, democratic member councils and lightweight operational arrangements. Funding tends to rely on institutional contributions, European Commission contracts, project funding, membership-related mechanisms, or support from a parent/foundation structure. Long-term sustainability may be vulnerable when funding depends heavily on one contract, one institution or one external funding stream.</p>

ERIC	The establishment process was generally described as long, negotiation-intensive, and politically demanding. Key hurdles included the need to secure Member State commitment, bridge the gap between project funding and legal establishment, manage host-country legal issues, and deal with national rules on HR, VAT, accounting, and administration. Statute changes may also become difficult as membership grows.	ERICs require a strong administrative core, formal governance bodies such as a General Assembly, Board of Directors and Scientific Advisory Board, as well as national coordination structures. Funding generally combines membership fees, in-kind contributions, national support, and EU projects. Membership fees alone are usually insufficient, making funding diversification important.
EDIC	The EDIC model was described as promising but still relatively new. Challenges included convincing Member States, identifying the right ministerial contacts, negotiating statutes and governance documents, and clarifying unresolved issues around VAT, state aid, economic activity, KPIs and national implementation structures. In some cases, an additional national legal vehicle was needed to operate locally.	EDIC governance was seen as flexible and adaptable, but it requires careful design to avoid excessive bureaucracy or founder capture. Funding models combine Member State contributions, EU projects, national or institutional support and, in some cases, public-private partnerships. User and community representation was considered especially important where the EDIC makes a long-term promise to users.

Table 2: Summary of key findings from the analysis of legal forms (Source: Borin, Cringoli, Giordino & Puhr 2026)

The comparative interview analysis suggests that the Cultural Heritage Cloud should adopt a staged legal strategy, beginning with a flexible transitional form and progressing towards a more structured and durable legal entity. This is indeed the basis for the proposals in the following chapter, for which the Complementary Paper “A Framework Analysis of European Legal Entities” (Borin, Cringoli, Giordino & Puhr 2026) provides data evidence.

2. The Future Legal Entity

The following section presents a proposed legal framework for the Cultural Heritage Cloud. It describes the structural model and governance architecture of the future legal entity, rather than its internal processes, which will be developed in upcoming tasks and formalised in the AISBL's statutes. In accordance with the ECHOES General Assembly decision of 14th April 2026, this section should be read as a base for discussion among partners and Member States. As such, the final decision made by all the interested partners, and the detailed decision-making processes selected for the Cloud legal entity, are subject to change.

As described in the Cultural Heritage Cloud Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA, D11.1), the future legal entity for the Cultural Heritage Cloud must be designed in direct alignment with its mission and long-term vision. The Cloud exists to overcome fragmentation in the European cultural heritage landscape by enabling collaborative creation, preservation, enrichment, and reuse of digital heritage knowledge within an open, community-driven digital ecosystem. It is conceived as a shared, trusted environment co-developed by and for the cultural heritage community, ensuring long-term accessibility, interoperability, and reuse of data and services beyond individual projects.

By 2035, the ECCCH aims to function as a self-sustaining, open, and sovereign European infrastructure under transparent public governance, where cultural heritage data flows seamlessly across institutions, disciplines, and borders. It is envisioned as a Digital Commons built around Heritage Digital Twins, a shared Knowledge Base, and advanced digital services, supporting research, education, policy, and creative reuse as a public good.

This mission and vision require a legal structure that guarantees openness, neutrality, and long-term sustainability; supports inclusive participation regardless of institutional size; protects European data sovereignty; and is capable of operating both shared services and collective governance.

2.1 Pathway towards Cultural Heritage Cloud EDIC

The proposed framework combines short-term operational feasibility with a clear long-term European ambition through a two-step strategy that secures continuity beyond the project phase while progressively converging towards a sustainable, Member State-anchored European structure.

This approach is designed to avoid a governance or operational gap at the end of the project and to mitigate the risks associated with the premature establishment of a complex European legal entity.

In a first phase, a lean AISBL provides immediate legal personality and operational capacity. In a second phase, the experience acquired through the AISBL is leveraged to support the transition towards an EDIC, ensuring that governance, financial, and operational mechanisms are tested under real conditions before being scaled up. This staged strategy reflects a pragmatic balance between short-term feasibility and long-term ambition, allowing the Cultural Heritage Cloud to remain operational, credible, and inclusive while preparing for long-term institutionalisation in line with EU policy priorities.

1 The Cultural Heritage Cloud AISBL

Creating the Cultural Heritage Cloud AISBL is the first operational step of the strategy and institutionalisation process. It is the most appropriate legal vehicle for the initial consolidation phase of the Cultural Heritage Cloud.

From the outset, its establishment is grounded in the alignment of the Cloud vision and mission, ensuring that the legal structure directly supports the initiative's public-interest objectives, core values, and service orientation. Designed to remain deliberately lean, the AISBL focuses on executive and operational functions, including coordination activities, infrastructure and service deployment, financial administration, and contractual relations. During the ECCCH funding phase, it is closely linked to the ECCCH project coordination teams and infrastructure partners.

At this early stage, the AISBL is also conceived to provide the institutional capacity required for the Cloud to operate in domains where cultural heritage, public interest, and regulatory or protection-related responsibilities intersect. The Cloud is intended to support not only scholarly and institutional collaboration, but also the long-term stewardship of provenance-related information, cross-border data sharing with public authorities, and governance frameworks capable of handling differentiated access to sensitive data. Establishing a legally accountable and neutral entity from the outset ensures that such uses can be integrated coherently within the Cloud as it develops, rather than requiring retrofitted governance arrangements at a later stage.

The AISBL is particularly suited to this role because it was expressly conceived to support international, cross-border cooperation within a European legal environment. Unlike national association forms, originally designed for domestic purposes and later adapted for international activities, the AISBL is intrinsically international in mandate and non-economic in purpose. This makes it naturally suited to hosting a European-level initiative during its start-up and early consolidation phase.

Its governance model further reinforces its relevance. The AISBL enables multi-stakeholder and participatory governance, allowing public authorities, research organisations, cultural institutions, infrastructure providers, and other actors from different countries to participate on an equal footing. While foreign participation is often possible under national legal forms, few are as naturally equipped to host genuine transnational, multi-member governance arrangements. This flexibility represents a decisive advantage for an initiative whose success depends on cross-border coordination and trust-building.

The Belgian legal context strengthens the suitability of the AISBL. Belgium offers a stable, predictable legal environment closely aligned with the established institutional practice. Hence, establishing the Cultural Heritage Cloud as a Belgian international non-profit association prevents it from becoming too closely tied to any single Member State's legal system, thereby preserving institutional neutrality that is essential at this early stage.

Operationally, the AISBL integrates the existing executive governance of the ECHOES project, ensuring continuity in leadership and decision-making while avoiding duplication of bodies. Broader advisory, strategic, and community-oriented governance structures remain at the network or project ecosystem level, allowing the AISBL to operate efficiently within a distributed governance landscape.

The AISBL is also well aligned with EU funding frameworks. It is a legal form widely recognised by European institutions and frequently used by European networks, alliances, and consortia. Its governance standards, transparency requirements, and legal personality closely match EU expectations, enabling the Cultural Heritage Cloud to engage credibly with European programmes while its long-term institutional model matures.

Finally, the AISBL offers a pragmatic compromise between robustness and speed. While its establishment requires notarial intervention and royal authorisation, it can typically be created within a matter of weeks, significantly faster than many recognised public interest structures in other Member States. This ensures rapid operational continuity beyond the project phase.

The AISBL is conceived from the outset as a transitional and preparatory structure, not as an end state. As a private law entity, it does not provide the intergovernmental standing and formal EU institutional recognition that the long-term operation of the ECCCH would require. The EDIC is one governance model worth examining for that stage, offering a framework aligned with the Digital Decade; the ERIC remains another credible option, particularly given its track record in research infrastructure governance. In either case, the AISBL serves as a deliberate bridge: enabling immediate operationalisation while the conditions for a longer-term legal structure are progressively assembled.

2 The EDIC (and the AISBL)

It is proposed that the EDIC constitute the long-term target structure for the Cultural Heritage Cloud legal entity. This recommendation responds to a combination of policy alignment, scale requirements, governance needs, and long-term sustainability objectives that cannot be addressed by lighter or transitional legal forms alone.

The Cultural Heritage Cloud is intrinsically linked to the objectives of the Digital Decade Policy Programme 2030, particularly regarding data infrastructures, artificial intelligence, and the reuse of public interest data. Within this framework, the EDIC has been explicitly identified at the EU level as the preferred legal instrument for cross-border digital infrastructures of strategic relevance, and is therefore proposed as the most coherent long-term structure for an initiative designed to operate at the European scale and support coordinated public policies across Member States.

This alignment is especially significant in the context of the Cloud cooperation with the common European data space for cultural heritage, recognised under the European Strategy for Data as a flagship initiative for Europe's digital future, and reinforced by a Joint Statement in March 2026. Anchoring the Cultural Heritage Cloud within an EDIC framework would directly respond to the European Commission's consistent calls for robust institutional frameworks, sustained public involvement, and long-term operational capacity to ensure the maturity and durability of data spaces.

It is further proposed that the EDIC framework's inherent flexibility be leveraged to accommodate the evolving nature of the initiative. It would enable research, innovation, and deployment activities to coexist within a single coherent institutional horizon, allowing the Cultural Heritage Cloud to evolve gradually from experimental developments to operational services and broad uptake by cultural institutions and public authorities.

From a governance perspective, it is proposed that the EDIC statutes be designed to ensure sustained Member State leadership through a structural voting majority, while enabling structured participation from research organisations, cultural heritage institutions, and other ecosystem actors through advisory and operational bodies.

This gradual and representative model would preserve public accountability while remaining open to the full breadth of the cultural heritage community. From a sustainability perspective, the EDIC would address the structural limitations of project-based funding by enabling a hybrid financing model combining EU-level instruments such as Digital Europe, Horizon Europe, and the Connecting Europe Facility, alongside Member State contributions and complementary revenue streams compatible with a public-interest mission, thereby reducing dependency on project cycles and supporting the progressive consolidation of services.

Within this overall strategy, it is proposed that the AISBL continue to play a complementary and preparatory role during the transition period, ensuring short-term operational continuity while progressively aligning governance practices, partnerships, and service models with EDIC requirements, providing a coherent pathway from experimentation and coordination towards durable European implementation.

(3) Towards an EDIC-only model?

Subject to political, legal and financial conditions, the two-step strategy allows for a convergence towards an EDIC-only model. In this scenario, the AISBL functions strictly as a transitional vehicle, ensuring continuity of operations until the EDIC becomes fully operational.

Once the EDIC assumes responsibility for governance, service provision and sustainability, the AISBL may be integrated into the EDIC or phased out in an orderly manner. However, this final decision will be that of the AISBL and the EDIC General Assembly. It will also be guided by the potential evolution of the EDIC framework, including the participation pathways for key actors of the field in Horizon Europe Associated Countries such as the UK.

Managing transition periods

The Cloud will undergo two main transition periods. The first will involve transitioning from the project phase to the AISBL in the short term. The second will be the move from the AISBL to the EDIC, with the potential aim of the latter becoming the sole ECCCH legal entity in the future. In both cases, the transition is expected to take time and involve a period of coexistence between the two entities.

During the first phase, the AISBL is to be established before the ECHOES project is concluded and will function in a complementary manner to it. They will therefore coexist until the end of ECHOES in June 2029, thus providing the opportunity to test the governance structure and refine it if necessary. It will also enable the AISBL to become financially operational by receiving funds and applying for grants. The primary aim here would be to ensure a smooth transition from the project to the final legal entity (i.e. the EDIC if this strategy is adopted), thus mitigating the financial and governance strains that commonly affect European projects when transitioning to infrastructures.

This process also entails ensuring the transition from some ECHOES and sister projects' agreements – including memoranda of understanding signed with other projects, initiatives, infrastructures or entities – to other legal instruments better suited to collaboration in the new entity, such as service level agreements. These will then need to be transferred and may need to be updated or reestablished when the EDIC is created.

The transition from the project to the AISBL will form part of the work carried out under Task 1.4 *Establishing ECCCH cross-project governance and transferring project outcomes to the legal entity* (M1–M60), led by the *Fondation des Sciences du Patrimoine*. This task will also anticipate the transition from the AISBL to the EDIC if this governance strategy is adopted in terms of decision authority, membership continuity, transfer of responsibility and results, financial continuity and governance overlap, based on the examples of AISBL that transitioned into either ERICs or EDICs.

2.2 The Cloud AISBL and EDIC governance models

The European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage phased approach reflects a deliberate legal strategy: establishing operational capacity and membership base under a flexible Belgian law framework before transitioning to the more robust, EU-regulated EDIC instrument. Each phase introduces new governance layers, expanded membership rights, and increased institutional accountability commensurate with the organisation's growing mandate and public funding responsibilities.

The Cloud AISBL governance

Figure 1: Recommended AISBL core governance structure

At its core, the AISBL is intentionally kept lean. Its primary governing body is the Assemblée Générale, composed of AISBL members, which retains strategic oversight responsibilities. The General Assembly validates high-level orientations, approves budgets and annual plans, admits new members, and ensures alignment with the long-term objectives that will eventually be transferred to the EDIC framework.

The Executive Organ of the AISBL integrates the current ECHOES project Coordination through its Executive Board. This integrated executive body is responsible for the day-to-day management of the initiative, including operational execution, infrastructure

deployment, service and platform development, financial administration, and coordination with stakeholders and funders. By embedding the existing executive leadership into the AISBL, the governance model ensures immediate operational capacity while avoiding institutional discontinuities.

Where necessary, additional institutions may be invited to join the Executive Organ to ensure adequate representation of operational, technical, or geographical capacity.

Decision-making within the Executive Organ follows clearly defined mandates delegated by the Assemblée Générale. Operational decisions are taken collegially, while specific responsibilities are allocated to designated coordinators or task leads to maintain efficiency and accountability.

Articulation with the ECHOES project governance

All other governance bodies established under the ECHOES project, such as advisory boards, scientific or technical committees, user or community panels, and work-package-level coordination structures, remain within the ECHOES project governance framework. These bodies continue to provide expertise, community representation, quality assurance, and strategic guidance without being formally absorbed into the AISBL to focus on execution and legal-financial responsibilities, while benefiting from the broader participatory and consultative ecosystem already in place.

Formal liaison mechanisms ensure alignment between the AISBL Executive Organ and the ECHOES governance bodies. This includes regular reporting, cross-participation of key individuals, and structured feedback loops, ensuring that strategic recommendations, scientific priorities, and community needs inform operational decisions.

Distributed and future-oriented governance

Governance is conceived not solely as a function of the legal entity, but as a distributed system spanning legal, technical and community layers. Operational authority resides in the AISBL Executive Organ, strategic legitimacy is anchored in the General Assembly and advisory structures, while implementation and innovation are distributed across project partners, service providers and thematic or technical working groups.

This distributed model allows governance mechanisms, such as decision workflows, accountability arrangements, and stakeholder engagement practices, to be tested, refined, and documented during the ECHOES project period. The experience gathered feeds directly into the design of the future EDIC governance structure, reducing transition risks and ensuring that the EDIC is founded on proven, operationally sound arrangements rather than abstract governance designs.

The Cloud EDIC governance

Figure 2: Recommended EDIC core governance structure

The governance structure of the Cultural Heritage Cloud under the European Digital Infrastructure Consortium (EDIC) model is designed to ensure a clear separation between strategic authority, advisory functions, executive responsibility, and operational implementation. This structured approach guarantees accountability, efficiency in decision-making, and the long-term sustainability of the infrastructure, while enabling responsiveness to scientific, technical, and societal developments.

Assembly of Members (AM)

As the highest body of the Cloud governance framework, the Assembly of Members (AM) constitutes the supreme decision-making body of the EDIC. Composed primarily of representatives of Member States, and potentially including associated or non-state members, the Assembly exercises ultimate authority over the strategic direction and institutional development of the Cultural Heritage Cloud.

The Assembly is responsible for adopting the multiannual strategy, annual work programmes, and budgetary allocations, as well as endorsing major evolutions of the infrastructure, including significant architectural or policy changes. It also defines the governance framework itself through the adoption of statutes and implementing rules, thereby ensuring legal clarity and institutional coherence.

In addition to its strategic role, the Assembly exercises oversight over the executive function, notably the Director, ensuring that decisions are implemented in accordance with the agreed objectives and the applicable legal framework. All decisions with legal, financial, or structural implications remain within its exclusive remit, reinforcing its central role in safeguarding the public interest and long-term viability of the Cloud.

Community Advisory Board (CAB)

The Community Advisory Board (CAB) functions as the principal advisory interface between the Cloud and its user communities, ensuring that the infrastructure remains aligned with scientific standards, user needs, and societal expectations.

The CAB is structured around specialised expert groups, including the Science and Users Group, the Technical Assessment Group, and the Legal and Ethics Group. Through these components, the CAB provides a multidimensional perspective covering scientific relevance, technical robustness, and regulatory compliance.

Its primary role is to deliver structured, evidence-based, and non-binding recommendations to the Director and, where appropriate, to the Assembly of Members. These recommendations concern the onboarding of services and datasets, the evolution of technical architecture, and policy development. The CAB also plays a key role in collecting and interpreting community feedback, particularly regarding usability, adoption barriers, and research impact.

While the CAB does not hold formal decision-making powers, it represents a critical mechanism for ensuring that the Cloud remains user-driven, scientifically credible, and responsive to stakeholder needs, thereby strengthening legitimacy and fostering community engagement.

Strategic Orientation Committee (SOC)

The Strategic Orientation Committee (SOC) complements the work of the Assembly of Members by providing high-level, forward-looking strategic advice. Its role is to support long-term positioning and ensure coherence with broader European and international developments in digital infrastructures, cultural heritage, and research policy.

The SOC contributes to the identification of emerging trends, technological opportunities, and policy challenges, enabling the EDIC to anticipate change and adapt proactively. It also facilitates alignment with cross-sectoral initiatives and reinforces synergies with other European infrastructures and programmes.

Although the SOC does not exercise formal decision-making authority, its recommendations inform the Assembly's deliberations and contribute to shaping the long-term vision and strategic priorities of the Cultural Heritage Cloud.

Supervisory Body and Operational Units

The Supervisory Body is chaired by the EDIC Director and operates at the intersection between strategic governance and operational execution. It is composed of the Director and a limited number of members, all appointed by the Assembly of Members. The Director acts as the legal representative of the EDIC and is entrusted with the implementation of the decisions adopted by the Assembly of Members.

In this capacity, the Director ensures the day-to-day management of the infrastructure and supervises both the technical governance bodies and the operational units. The Director is responsible for translating strategic orientations into concrete actions, preparing decision proposals, and ensuring compliance with legal, financial, and regulatory requirements.

Supporting the Supervisory Body, the Operational Units provide the administrative and technical backbone necessary for the functioning of the Cloud.

Administrative and Governance Support Unit

The administrative component of the operational structure acts as the central coordination and support mechanism for governance processes. It performs key functions such as the registration and processing of proposals, organisation of meetings, documentation of decisions, and maintenance of governance records.

It also manages monitoring systems and key performance indicators (KPIs), ensuring continuous oversight of technical performance, usage, interoperability, and sustainability metrics. By identifying risks, inconsistencies, or threshold breaches, this unit plays a crucial role in triggering escalation procedures and ensuring that issues are addressed in a timely and structured manner.

Technical Operations Unit (TechOps)

The Technical Operations Unit (TechOps) is responsible for the day-to-day technical functioning and reliability of the Cloud infrastructure. Its remit includes system monitoring, incident management, service continuity, cybersecurity measures, and infrastructure maintenance.

TechOps operates as the first line of response in case of technical incidents and ensures that services remain operational, secure, and performant. It collaborates closely with technical governance bodies, particularly the Technical Assessment Group, to ensure that operational practices remain aligned with architectural and interoperability standards.

2.4 Cloud governance and external collaboration

The governance of the Cultural Heritage Cloud is conceived in strong continuity with established European approaches to large-scale digital ecosystems, notably the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and the Common European Data Spaces.

These initiatives demonstrate that federated technical architectures require governance models that are both robust and adaptable, capable of coordinating distributed services, data providers, and user communities under shared rules while allowing for domain-specific innovation. The Cultural Heritage Cloud's governance is therefore designed to anticipate close alignment between its internal decision-making structures and the technical and policy governance mechanisms of these wider ecosystems, including interoperability standards, role-based participation, and compliance with EU legal and ethical frameworks.

Collaboration with stakeholders who will not be directly or indirectly members of the Cloud AISBL and then the Cloud EDIC can take several forms, which do not always need to be institutionalised. This section looks at how the proposed legal entities for the Cloud will be able to create formal governance partnerships with different types of partners. These partnerships can take several forms: reserved seats in advisory boards or technical boards, observer rights, joint roadmaps, joint ventures, contracts, etc.

Collaboration with private partners and innovation hubs

The Cultural Heritage Cloud is not solely a technical infrastructure: it is a sociotechnical system in which organisational practices, community norms, and digital tools are co-designed and mutually shaped. Innovation extends beyond the deployment of technologies to encompass the transformation of workflows, roles and collaborative arrangements within and across cultural heritage institutions, with the support of private partners.

The Cloud enables new forms of distributed knowledge production while, at the same time, requiring governance mechanisms to ensure these practices remain aligned with open science principles and the professional values of heritage communities. The sociotechnical dimension is reflected in the modular, federated architecture of the Cloud, which separates the technical layer from community governance and scientific steering, while maintaining structured interfaces between them.

This design will directly impact the selection of the most appropriate framework for collaboration with private partners and innovation hubs. Partners with a thematic interest in technological development can be invited to join as contractors, members technical boards or working groups, partner with specific policy objectives that align with the Cloud, and can be invited to sign a Memorandum of Understanding or a Joint Roadmap, while partners with the highest strategic alignment with the Cloud vision and mission can be invited to join the future Strategic Orientation Committee. or, in rare cases, the supervisory body of the Cloud.

In this perspective, the sociotechnical innovation capacity of the Cloud also depends on interoperability and structured dialogue with established European digital and research infrastructures, including EOSC, the Data Space for Cultural Heritage, and selected ERICs and AI Factories. As highlighted in the ECHOES First Policy Brief,³ successful integration with Cultural Heritage Data Digital Commons relies on shared standards and common interoperability mechanisms across datasets, services and AI workflows, which function as key instruments of governance within a federated ecosystem.

These mechanisms enable structured collaboration between public institutions, research infrastructures and industrial and technology partners and should help reduce fragmentation across the broader European Data Spaces and Europeana Research Area landscapes.

Collaboration with communities via umbrella organisations and networks

As highlighted by the ECHOES Community building strategy, establishing a network of trust requires active participation from both individuals and professional umbrella organisations and networks. These relationships will also support collaboration around capacity-building, data policy, and advocacy across the wider cultural heritage and research ecosystem.

While the detailed participation mechanisms for individuals are described in the community-building strategy, the participation of umbrella organisations and networks will also vary based on the objective of the collaboration with the Cloud. Although partnership with these organisations can also be formalised through the options listed above, we expect that the better part of this collaboration will happen through the EDIC Community Advisory Board, once it is set up.

Coordination with Partnerships and key policy programmes

European policy programmes, as led by the European Commission, and Partnerships within Horizon Europe have a different nature than the partners in the above sections. Their participation in the Cloud governance will take different forms.

³ Petitcol, R., *et al.* (2026) *First Policy Brief (D10.3)*.

While the European Commission and, when relevant, other national policymakers, can be expected to have meaningful decision-making authority within the future highest decision-making bodies of the Cloud governance, collaborative European Partnerships, or similar initiatives such as Joint Programming Initiatives will require formal agreements with the Cloud governance.

These agreements will first be negotiated by ECHOES and could be gradually endorsed by the Cloud AISBL before a transition to the Cloud EDIC. The ongoing discussion with the Partnership for Resilient Cultural Heritage (RCH) will constitute a real-life test for collaboration between the governance of two large initiatives in the field of Cultural Heritage based on joint objectives and activities.

The Cloud governance and international collaboration

International collaboration, meaning collaboration with non-EU partners, is also envisaged through two main options:

- Direct participation in the Cloud AISBL and EDIC, provided that the third-country or institution is eligible to do so. The detailed eligibility criteria for participating in the AISBL and the EDIC will be further defined later in the next years of ECHOES, based on Belgian and European Union rules, respectively.
- Participation through the use of Memorandums of Understanding or other forms of binding or non-binding agreements between the Cloud legal entity and third parties. This approach is already gradually being implemented by ECHOES, especially through its Integration Task Force and Stakeholder Council.

As stated in the first chapter of this document, non-EU but European countries that have already expressed interest in the Cultural Heritage Cloud by participating in ECCCH projects, such as the UK, are the primary target for direct participation in the Cloud governance.

The rest of the Cloud internationalisation strategy, including strategic partnerships with non-EU partners, is further described in the ECHOES SRIA.⁴

⁴ Demetrescu, E., et al. (2026) ECCCH's Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (D11.1).

3. Technical governance

The technical governance of the Cultural Heritage Cloud must ensure that the Cloud evolves in a controlled, transparent, and sustainable way, while remaining scientifically relevant, technically coherent, user-driven, and compliant with legal and ethical requirements. In line with other examples taken from existing digital infrastructures and digital commons, the technical governance is conceived as an integrated system that combines decision-making, recurring technical review, operational monitoring, expert assessment, and structured escalation paths (see Annex 1). Because not all technical decisions require high-level decision makers to intervene, the Cloud technical governance only partly overlaps with the formal statutory decision-making bodies recommended in Chapter 2.

The objectives of the Cloud technical governance are:

- Ensuring the long-term **architectural coherence** of the Cloud.
- **Controlled evolution**: ensuring that new services, datasets, workflows, and technical changes are assessed consistently before they are accepted into the ecosystem.
- **Risk management**: creating mechanisms for reacting when problems appear, whether these concern interoperability, security, performance, usability, or sustainability.
- **Continuity**: providing a stable bridge between project-time implementation and post-project operation.

A good technical governance model must clearly distinguish between strategic authority, expert advisory and validation roles, and operational execution. This separation of functions reduces the risk that too many operational issues are escalated to the highest level, or that important technical and operational questions remain unresolved because nobody is clearly responsible for triggering a decision.

In the AISBL phase, these objectives are implemented through a lean governance structure that integrates existing ECHOES executive mechanisms, while keeping advisory and community bodies largely at the project level. In the EDIC phase, the same technical governance bodies are placed under the authority of the Supervisory Body and the Director, with clear provisions in the EDIC Statutes and internal rules on mandates, decision-making and accountability to the Assembly of Members.

3.1. Technical governance in the EDIC model

In the envisaged EDIC, the Assembly of Members holds the highest strategic authority, including approval of the work programme, budget, and major evolutions of the infrastructure. It delegates day-to-day management to the Director, who acts as the legal representative and is responsible for implementing the Assembly's decisions in accordance with the Statutes and the host state's legal framework.

Technical governance bodies operate under the authority of the Director as supervising authority, and their mandates are specified in implementing rules adopted by the Assembly. Their role is to:

- Provide structured expert input to the Director and, where relevant, to the Assembly.
- Issue technical, scientific, legal, ethical or user-oriented opinions, validations and recommendations.
- Monitor defined indicators and thresholds.
- Trigger escalation to the Director and, for matters of strategic impact, to the Assembly of Members.

Formal decisions with legal or financial consequences (e.g. service acceptance, contractual commitments, policy adoption) remain the responsibility of the Director and/or the Assembly, in accordance with the EDIC Statutes and host-state law. This clarifies that expert bodies contribute to and prepare decisions, but do not themselves carry the EDIC's legal responsibility.

During the AISBL phase, the same logic applies *mutatis mutandis*: the General Assembly exercises strategic oversight, and the Executive Organ ensures implementation, while the technical governance bodies operate as advisory and validation structures under delegated authority.

3.2. Communities within technical governance

The EDIC Community Advisory Board combines scientific alignment with user-driven steering. Its role is to ensure that the Cloud remains both scientifically relevant and genuinely useful for its target communities.

The Community Advisory Board is governed by its own rules of procedure. Depending on the timing of the establishment of the AISBL and the EDIC, this EDIC body could first be started as an AISBL activity, with continuity of membership and procedures where possible.

Within the Community Advisory Body, a **Science and Users Group**:

- advises the Director and Assembly on scientific strategy, methodological relevance, and the quality of research-oriented outputs;
- ensures alignment with heritage science priorities and FAIR/open science principles, taking into account the broader European research infrastructure landscape;
- reviews whether services, workflows, and data models support meaningful research practices and realistic user journeys for target communities such as museums, researchers, cultural heritage practitioners, infrastructures and data providers;
- collects and interprets structured feedback on usability, adoption barriers, and community value, in coordination with user engagement activities and work packages;
- issues non-binding opinions on service and dataset onboarding, architecture changes and policy updates from the perspective of scientific relevance and user impact.
-

It does not take binding decisions. The Supervisory Body, the Director, and the Assembly of Members take the recommendations into account in preparing proposals and decisions.

3.3. Technical Assessment Group

Like the Science and Users Group, the **Technical Assessment Group** is an offshoot of the Community Advisory Board. It is the primary expert body responsible for technical quality, interoperability, architectural consistency, and technical risk. Its mandate covers the validations of architectural choices, APIs, data standards, technical readiness, operational maturity, and conformance with the cloud architecture.

For minor changes within the scope defined by the Assembly (e.g. updates that do not affect legal obligations, funding decisions, or core interoperability guarantees), the Technical Assessment Group may be mandated by internal rules to issue approvals that the Director can implement directly. For major changes, the Technical Assessment Group's role is to prepare a motivated recommendation that the Director submits to the Assembly for decision.

The Group is responsible for:

- reviewing and validating architectural choices, APIs, standards, interoperability levels, SLAs and deployment assumptions against the cloud architecture defined in WP6 and subsequent design work;
- assessing cybersecurity, performance, resilience, and operational maturity of services and datasets proposed for onboarding;
- conducting technology readiness assessments and risk-based technical monitoring, including periodic audits of critical components;
- reviewing proposed changes to architecture, supported formats, technical policies, and interoperability rules, and classifying them as minor (within the Director’s mandate) or major (requiring Assembly involvement);
- issuing formal technical opinions for service onboarding, incident postmortems and policy update proposals, to be integrated by the Director into decision packages.

The ECHOES Integration Task Force and the Technical Assessment Group shall remain distinct, but their relationship should be clearly defined in their potential two years of coexistence. The ECHOES Integration Task Force is an operational coordination mechanism, not a formal decision-making body. It operates across project partners, service providers and technical work packages to prepare integration cases for review by the technical governance bodies.

The ECHOES Integration Task Force should act as the coordination and preparation layer. Its role would be to identify integration needs, gather cases from projects and partners, clarify scope, connect the relevant actors, and prepare issues for structured review. It should help contributions move forward and resolve practical cross-WPs or cross-project questions early, before they become formal governance decisions.

The Technical Assessment Group, in turn, should act as the technical governance and assurance layer. Its role would be to review those cases that have architectural, interoperability, security, operational, or technical quality implications, and to decide whether the proposed integration or change is acceptable in the proposed form.

In this model, the process should work as follows:

1. ECHOES Integration Task Force identifies, shapes, and coordinates integration cases.
2. Technical Assessment Group reviews and validates cases that require formal technical assessment.
3. ECHOES Integration Task Force then helps implement, communicate, and follow up on the outcome of that assessment.

3.4. Legal and Ethics Council

The Legal and Ethics Group is the last internal group of the Community Advisory Board. Following an internal selection process, it is composed of individuals with proven expertise in legal and ethics matters related but not limited to cultural heritage or digital topics.

Its role is to ensure that the technical evolution of the Cloud remains legally compliant and ethically responsible throughout both the AISBL and EDIC phases. This includes GDPR, copyright, licensing, data access conditions, AI Act-related constraints, cultural sensitivity, provenance transparency, and responsible reuse.

The Legal and Ethics Group:

- reviews proposals for services, datasets, workflows and policy changes against EU and national law, including GDPR, the Data Act, the AI Act, copyright and neighbouring rights, open data legislation, and other relevant instruments.
- assesses ethical risks linked to provenance, data usage, cultural sensitivity, algorithmic transparency and potential biases.
- issues guidance on licencing models (including open licences), access categories, data governance patterns and responsible AI use.
- participates in incident and security response processes, especially where data breaches, unlawful processing, or high-risk AI systems are involved, and advises on notification obligations to supervisory authorities.
- contributes to sustainability and post-project transition discussions wherever service models, data retention, or changes in legal responsibility may affect rights and obligations.

3.5. Operating the Cloud Technical Governance

The Operational Unit

The Operational Unit serves as the backbone for the execution and coordination of governance processes. Depending on the development and exploitation phase of the Cultural Heritage Cloud, this unit is embodied by the executive team of ECHOES, then by the AISBL and ultimately by the EDIC. It acts as the central service desk and secretariat for technical governance. Its responsibilities include:

- registering proposals and incident reports, checking completeness, and routing issues to the appropriate governance bodies;
- organising meetings, managing agendas and minutes, and maintaining documentation and decision logs;
- running monitoring and KPI dashboards, including technical, usage, interoperability and sustainability indicators;
- detecting when thresholds are exceeded, when proposals are incomplete, or when conflicts between boards arise, and initiating escalation to the Director;
- coordinating communication and follow-up actions once decisions have been taken by the Director or Assembly.

The “TechOps” Unit

The Technical Operations Unit, or “TechOps” is distinct from the Operational Unit. It coordinates governance; the Technical Operations Unit ensures technical operations. The Technical Operations Unit should handle runtime monitoring, operational incidents, service continuity, patching, platform reliability, and first-line operational response. The Integration Task Force is also a distinguished body: it is coordination and planning oriented, while Technical Operations is service-delivery and runtime oriented.

Similar to the Operational Unit, its placement within the overall governance of the Cloud depends on the development and exploitation of the Cloud. It is placed under project coordination, and then the AISBL and EDIC directors’ responsibility.

The suggested operational processes for cultural governance in the first phase of its deployment are detailed in [Annex 1](#).

4. The Cloud governance and the fight against illicit trafficking of cultural goods

The Cultural Heritage Cloud is being designed as one of the most significant digital platforms for cultural heritage in Europe. In the coming years, it is expected to host, connect, and make interoperable an unprecedented volume of documentation on cultural objects, collections, sites, and their histories, progressively becoming a central reference point for heritage professionals, institutions, researchers, and public authorities across the continent.

This centrality carries a specific responsibility. Cultural heritage data infrastructures are not neutral instruments: depending on how they are governed, they can either actively support the protection of cultural property or, if insufficiently regulated, risk becoming vectors of opacity and misuse. The illicit trafficking of cultural goods (TCG) thrives precisely where documentation is fragmented, provenance is obscure, and institutional oversight is absent. A large-scale, under-governed cloud infrastructure could inadvertently reinforce these conditions.

It is therefore necessary that the governance framework of the Cloud be designed from the outset with a clear awareness of its potential role in countering illicit trafficking. This chapter addresses that question directly, mapping the phenomenon and its institutional landscape before articulating a set of governance-oriented recommendations aimed at shaping the Cloud as a responsible and protection-conscious infrastructure, highlighting its potential and possible limits, especially given the current international situation, in which ongoing conflicts have brought the issue of illicit trafficking of cultural goods to the forefront.

4.1 The phenomenon of illicit trafficking of cultural heritage: scope, dynamics, and stakeholders

Illicit trafficking in cultural goods constitutes one of the most structurally complex forms of transnational crime in the European landscape, operating at the intersection of the legitimate art and antiquities trade and organised criminal activity. Its damage is simultaneously material and immaterial, eroding communities' access to their own historical and cultural identity. Looted objects have been described as “cultural orphans, which, torn from their contexts, remain forever dumb and virtually useless for scholarly purposes” (Cannon-Brookes, 1994), a formulation that captures the irreversibility of the epistemic loss that accompanies each illicit excavation or thievery.

Measuring the scale of TCG is notoriously difficult: the phenomenon unfolds in a grey market where licit and illicit transactions are often indistinguishable, and the dark figure of undetected crime is structurally large (Brodie et al., 2022). The illicit segment of the art market represents a substantial and persistent economic reality whose full contours remain opaque. Interpol Work of Art Unit's annual reports record several thousand stolen or seized objects across European jurisdictions, with hundreds of confirmed illicit excavation sites documented in recent years (Interpol, 2021; 2022). The burden of proof remains a structurally near-insurmountable obstacle for law enforcement: illicitly excavated objects are not registered in any public collection prior to their removal, and prosecution must demonstrate both the object's pre-excavation belonging to the source state and its illegal export after the entry into force of a relevant legal instrument, a task that in practice renders the majority of trafficking acts legally unpunishable (Mackenzie, 2025).

TCG conventionally distinguishes source, transit, and destination countries: a tripartite model that has become increasingly fluid in the digital era. Europe is simultaneously a major source region for archaeological looting, particularly across the Mediterranean basin and in conflict-affected areas of Eastern Europe, where the war in Ukraine has added urgent new dimensions to the problem of heritage at risk; a transit zone for objects moving through free ports, dealer networks, and auction infrastructures; and one of the world's primary destination markets. The European Commission has acknowledged that the scrutiny and control of trade in cultural goods varies widely within the single market, creating loopholes that traffickers systematically exploit (European Commission, COM(2022) 800 final).

The economics of extraction also vary markedly across regions. Criminal actors span a wide spectrum beyond excavators themselves. Dealers, restorers, false-expertise providers, and auction specialists fabricate or manipulate provenance documentation. Evidence has been gathered of scholars providing false letters of expertise, catalogue authors selectively omitting provenance data to prevent red flags, and restorers intervening extensively on objects to conceal evidence of illicit excavation (Leeson et al., 2026). The phenomenon of scholarly facilitation has been analysed in recent research as a structural feature of the trafficking supply chain rather than an exceptional deviance (Smith, 2025). Auction catalogue narratives have similarly been shown to actively construct consumer desire around unprovenanced objects, suppressing due diligence through marketing practices that normalise the absence of documentation (Yates, 2025). High-profile prosecutions illustrate the international reach of these networks, the involvement of established cultural institutions, and the mixed deterrent signals that high-profile cases send to the market (Mackenzie, 2025).

The results of Operation Pandora, coordinated annually by Europol since 2016, provide the most operationally concrete available indicator of the scale and geographic distribution of TCG in Europe. The eighth edition (Pandora VIII, 2023), led by the Spanish Guardia Civil with the support of Europol and INTERPOL and involving authorities from 25 countries, resulted in 85 arrests and the recovery of more than 6,400 cultural goods; several thousand checks were carried out at airports, ports, and border crossing points, as well as in auction houses and private residences, while 6,000 online checks led to the recovery of 580 stolen objects (Europol/INTERPOL, 2024). The ninth and most recent edition (Pandora IX, conducted throughout 2024 and published in May 2025), involving law enforcement and customs authorities from 23 countries and coordinated with operational support from Europol, INTERPOL, and the World Customs Organisation (WCO), delivered the most significant results in the operation's history: 80 arrests, the seizure of 37,727 cultural goods (including archaeological pieces, paintings, coins, icons, and musical instruments), the confiscation of 69 metal detectors (from those countries, like Italy, where the use of such tools is strictly regulated) and 23 tools for illegal excavation, and the opening of 258 cases (Europol/INTERPOL/WCO, 2025). Among Pandora IX's most operationally significant findings was the growing role of digital platforms as a channel of choice for traffickers: dedicated cyber patrols led to the seizure of 4,298 objects offered for sale through social media, online marketplaces, and dedicated websites, demonstrating that the grey market has migrated substantially to digital environments where anonymity and global reach facilitate transactions that previously required physical proximity to specialised dealer networks. Specific actions under Pandora IX highlighted persistent geographic patterns: the dismantling of a criminal group in the province of Cáceres (Spain) that looted Roman coins from protected archaeological sites and sold them through social media; the recovery of 5 Byzantine icons in Athens through undercover operations; and the interception of 87 cultural goods illegally transported out of Ukraine to Poland, Moldova, and Romania (Europol/INTERPOL/WCO, 2025).

EU policy has framed TCG as a form of serious and organised crime under EMPACT 2022–2025, yet the analysis of 58 EU policy documents from 1993 to 2023 reveals conceptual deficits in this framing: an overemphasis on the organised crime characterisation risks producing policies blind to the genuine diversity of trafficking configurations and to the grey-market nature of the trade (Faraldo Cabana, 2025). Empirical research consistently shows that TCG is characterised by decentralised constellations of small networks often without common organisational patterns, and that links to terrorist financing, while documented in specific geopolitical contexts, remain insufficiently evidenced as a systemic feature of European TCG (Faraldo Cabana, 2024).

Recent scholarship has begun to shift analytical attention towards deterrence models that operate at the demand end of the supply chain, arguing that measures that dissuade dealers, collectors, and institutions from buying at the market end can affect the value chain and so deter looters at the source end: crime prevention in antiquities trafficking can be global in aim and effect (Mackenzie, 2025).

The prevention and enforcement landscape is multi-sectoral. Dedicated law enforcement units, such as the Carabinieri's *Comando Tutela Patrimonio Culturale* (Command for the Protection of Cultural Heritage - TPC, established in 1969), the French *Office central de lutte contre le trafic de biens culturels* (OCBC, established in 1975), and the Spanish *Heritage Brigade* of the National Police (established in 1977) are recognised centres of excellence, but remain exceptions: most EU member states handle heritage crimes through general police without dedicated training. The Carabinieri TPC's database currently holds over 7.9 million records, of which approximately 1.2 million remain to be recovered, the world's largest specialised database of its kind. Social sciences and humanities researchers provide the indispensable scholarly infrastructure (provenance studies, typological analysis, criminal network mapping) without which seized objects cannot be identified, attributed, or returned (Leeson et al., 2026; Smith, 2025). The structural deficits that persist provide the essential context for understanding how the Cultural Heritage Cloud can contribute to addressing the problem at a systemic level.

4.2 European legal and policy instruments to counter illicit trafficking

The normative framework governing the protection of cultural goods from illicit trafficking has evolved substantially over the past five decades, through successive layers of international conventions, European Union legislation, and national implementing measures.

At the international level, the foundational instrument remains the 1970 UNESCO *Convention on the Means of Prohibiting and Preventing the Illicit Import, Export and Transfer of Ownership of Cultural Property*. Ratified by 149 States Parties as of May 2026, the Convention establishes the principle that cultural property exported in violation of the laws of its state of origin should not be imported, sold, or transferred by other states, and obliges signatory states to take measures to prohibit the acquisition of illegally exported objects by museums and other institutions. While the 1970 Convention defines the key threshold (the date before which objects with undocumented provenance are presumed to be of potentially illicit origin) its implementation has been widely criticised as insufficiently binding, dependent on bilateral diplomatic arrangements, and poorly equipped to address the complexities of the contemporary art market (Brodie, 2014).

The 1995 UNIDROIT *Convention on Stolen or Illegally Exported Cultural Objects* addressed some of these lacunae by establishing more precise civil law remedies for the restitution and return of stolen or illegally exported objects, including limitation periods and good-faith purchaser provisions. Its more limited ratification (56 States Parties as of May 2026) reflects the resistance of major market states to accepting obligations that would impose more stringent due diligence requirements on their art markets.

At the UN Security Council level, *Resolution 2347* (2017), adopted unanimously in the context of the destruction and looting of cultural heritage by ISIL/Da'esh in Syria and Iraq, marked the first time the Security Council addressed the protection of cultural heritage as a peace and security issue, condemning illicit trafficking as a source of terrorist financing and calling upon member states to take measures to prevent the trade in cultural property from conflict zones. The resolution gave significant political impetus to European legislative efforts.

Within the European Union, the legal framework for combating TCG is structured around several complementary instruments. *Regulation (EC) No 116/2009* on the export of cultural goods establishes a system of export authorisation for significant cultural objects leaving EU customs territory, requiring licences issued by competent national authorities. Its implementation has been uneven across member states, and the Commission has acknowledged that the system is subject to variable scrutiny across the single market (European Commission, COM(2022) 800 final). *Directive 2014/60/EU* on the return of cultural objects unlawfully removed from the territory of a member state provides the legal basis for cross-border restitution claims within the EU, establishing a procedure by which requesting states can recover unlawfully removed objects held in other member states. Its practical impact has been limited by restrictive definitions of eligibility and short limitation periods.

The most significant recent legislative development is *Regulation (EU) 2019/880* of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 April 2019 on the introduction and the import of cultural goods, which became fully applicable on 28 June 2025. This Regulation introduces, for the first time, EU-wide import controls for cultural goods entering from outside the EU, distinguishing between objects for which an import licence is required and those for which an importer statement suffices. The Regulation also establishes a centralised electronic system for the processing and storage of import licences and importer statements (Import Cultural Goods - ICG).

This system represents a potential point of integration for the Cultural Heritage Cloud, and its design has direct implications for the data architecture and access governance of the Cloud's provenance registry. It is worth noting that the Regulation's full implementation is still in its early stages, and its practical effectiveness in addressing the manipulation of provenance claims remains to be assessed.

At the policy level, the European Commission's EU Action Plan against illicit trafficking of cultural goods (COM(2022) 800 final) sets out a comprehensive strategic framework, organised around four pillars: enhancing the legal framework, improving prevention and detection, strengthening cross-border cooperation, and raising public awareness. Relevant to the Cloud's governance design are several specific commitments in this Action Plan: to support the development of standardised provenance documentation practices; to promote interoperability between national databases of stolen objects and EU-level systems; to integrate cultural heritage expertise into law enforcement training; and to explore the potential of digital technologies (including AI, semantic data matching, and distributed databases) for object identification and provenance verification (European Commission, COM(2022) 800 final).

Two further international instruments deserve mention for their relevance to the governance context of the Cultural Heritage Cloud. The Council of Europe's *Faro Convention on the Value of Cultural Heritage for Society* (2005) establishes the principle that access to cultural heritage is a human right and imposes positive obligations on signatory states to facilitate participatory approaches to heritage management, a framing that supports the Cloud's inclusive, multi-stakeholder governance model. The Council of Europe *Convention on Offences relating to Cultural Property* (Nicosia Convention, 2017), while not yet widely ratified, provides a harmonised criminal law framework specifically designed for cultural heritage offences and encourages the development of national databases and international information-sharing mechanisms of direct relevance to the Cloud's design.

The normative framework described above has been put to action and refined through a sustained cycle of EU-funded projects which collectively constitute the most significant body of applied knowledge on TCG prevention and enforcement available to policymakers, spanning Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe and representing a total investment of several tens of millions of euros.

- [NETCHER](#) (H2020, G.A. 822585; 2019–2021), coordinated by CNRS, built the first large-scale European cross-sectoral network of TCG professionals spanning law enforcement, archaeology, museums, art market, and SSH research, and produced approximately 200 policy recommendations across four Policy Briefs
- [PITCHER](#) (Erasmus+, G.A. 2021-1-FR01-KA220-SCH-000032674; 2021–2024), coordinated by the French National Police Academy (ENSP), developed Open Educational Resources for secondary and higher education on archaeological looting and illicit trafficking. Its policy recommendations call for TCG content integration in national curricula, professional training on heritage protection obligations, and strengthened collaboration between educational institutions and law enforcement agencies.
- [RITHMS](#) (Horizon Europe, G.A. 101073932; 2022–2025), led by the Centre for Cultural Heritage Technology of IIT, developed an interoperable social network analysis (SNA)-based intelligence platform for LEAs integrating Open Source Intelligence (OSINT) data (e.g., cultural heritage repositories, auction data, and public stolen objects databases) with Call Data Records (CDRs), satellite data, and police restricted data. It produced the first large-scale non-police dataset of cultural goods, criminological analyses of TCG dynamics, a legal framework review across member states, and ontological contributions that feed directly into the ECHOES HDTO provenance extension.
- [ENIGMA](#) (Horizon Europe, G.A. 101094237; 2023–2025), coordinated by the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, develops digital tools for identification, traceability, and provenance research of cultural goods, alongside Earth observation-based monitoring of endangered sites.
- [AURORA](#) (Horizon Europe, G.A. 101094245; 2023–2025) developed an authentication system combining nanotechnological chemical markers, miniaturised tracking devices, and blockchain-based storage to create a stable physical-to-digital identity connection for each cultural object.
- [ANCHISE](#) (Horizon Europe, G.A. 101094824; 2023–2026) gathered diverse technological anti-trafficking solutions and developed a strategic institutional analysis proposing a European Interdisciplinary Competence Centre for Illicit Trafficking Combat.

4.3 Leveraging the Cultural Heritage Cloud to counter illicit trafficking

The Cloud as a framework for ‘provenance’ tracking and heritage protection

The Cultural Heritage Cloud is being designed to support heritage protection, *provenance* tracing, and risk management. Concretely, ECHOES promotes within the ontological framework a set of structured classes and properties directly relevant to the legal biography of an object drawing on CIDOC CRM and its extensions, especially CRMinf, and introducing three new classes and two new properties (HDTO: WP7, Task 7.1, D7.1).

An integrated and widespread use of the Cloud across multiple domains and cultural professional communities would substantially enhance risk assessment and recovery capabilities related to illicitly trafficked objects.

Cross-referencing and structured querying would allow competent authorities and professional users to flag objects whose physical characteristics and geographic attribution are inconsistent with their purported expressed narrative or provenance or, conversely, appear suspiciously similar to material deriving from recently reported illicit excavations, or to objects recently reported as stolen from a public or private collection in the Cloud ecosystem.

This form of “red flagging” and “risk assessment”, while not constituting legal proof per se, would be managed by the Cloud technical governance and significantly raise the threshold of due diligence required and discourage acquisitions or certifications that might otherwise proceed unchecked. The participation of cultural heritage umbrella organisations and networks in the Community Advisory Board would ensure an appropriate diffusion of this service, and their involvement in the different Board Groups described in the previous chapter would ensure compliance with the applicable legal and ethical standards.

An illustrative case study. The “Chariot of Eretum” and the other objects from Montelibretti tomb XI: the long road to restitution

The potential of the Cultural Heritage Cloud as an active tool against illicit trafficking is best understood through a concrete historical case, one that illustrates, with clarity, both the vulnerabilities of the current system and the opportunities that a Collaborative Cloud infrastructure might have created. The case of Tomb XI of the Colle del Forno necropolis and the extraordinary funerary assemblage, including the so-called “chariot of *Eretum*”, offers precisely this kind of instructive scenario.

In 1970, construction works at the “Roma 1” Research Area of the National Research Council of Italy (CNR), near Montelibretti (Rome), accidentally exposed a monumental chamber tomb belonging to the Colle del Forno necropolis, a site associated with the ancient Sabine city of *Eretum*, whose funerary deposits span from the late 7th to the early 3rd century BCE. That same night, illegal excavators equipped with mechanical tools stripped the tomb of its most significant contents, causing irreparable damage to the stratigraphy and tomb structure. The looted materials, including a remarkable ceremonial chariot decorated with bronze relief plates, came into the possession of Giacomo Medici, a dealer implicated in major trafficking operations of the period, including the removal of the Euphronios krater from Cerveteri. The artefacts, stored in Medici’s warehouse within the Geneva Free Port, were eventually acquired by the Ny Carlsberg Glyptotek in Copenhagen in the early 1970s, after extensive cleaning and restoration operations conducted in Zurich.

Figure 3: *Fara in Sabina (Rieti, Italy), Civic Archaeological Museum of Sabina Tiberina, the chariot of Eretum from Tomb XI of the Colle del Forno necropolis* (© Civic Archaeological Museum of Sabina Tiberina)

The scientific excavation of what remained of Tomb XI, conducted by CNR researchers in 1972, recovered the structural elements of the dromos, vestibule, and main chamber along with a modest assemblage of objects. It was the painstaking comparison of these excavated materials with the Copenhagen assemblage, first reported by the Ny Carlsberg Glyptotek in its 1979 institutional journal (*Meddelelser fra Ny Carlsberg Glyptotek*), that suggested a shared origin and the illicit export underwent by the artefacts. Subsequent scholarly collaboration confirmed the attribution of the Copenhagen assemblage to Tomb XI, leading eventually to a virtual reconstruction of the chariot and a collaborative exhibition held in Copenhagen in 2006. The formal restitution process was initiated only

in 2016, following the intervention of the Carabinieri TPC, which had seized Giacomo Medici's Polaroid archive, containing photographic documentation of the looted materials, as early as 1995. The return of the artefacts was formalised through a bilateral agreement between the Italian Ministry of Culture and the Ny Carlsberg Glyptotek. In 2024, following restoration work, the chariot and associated materials were permanently installed at the Civic Archaeological Museum of Fara in Sabina (Rieti), the institution closest to their site of origin (Benelli, Santoro, 2021; Betori, Licordari, 2021).

The above-mentioned case is, in many respects, representative of a generation of trafficking operations that exploited a series of structural vulnerabilities: the absence of real-time documentation at the moment of discovery, the lack of cross-institutional data sharing, the opacity of the pre-digital art market, and the lengthy timescales required for scholarly attribution to translate into legal action. Had an infrastructure like the Cultural Heritage Cloud been in place, several of these vulnerabilities might have been significantly mitigated.

Following the archaeological discovery, a structured digital record, including findspot data, basic photographic documentation, and a preliminary typological classification, later expandable through bibliographic references and further studies, could have been readily entered into the cloud by CNR researchers or the competent Superintendency officials, accompanied by the theft report.

When the curators of the Ny Carlsberg Glyptotek were presented with the lot for acquisition, a due diligence query against the cloud's cross-domain database, combining CNR excavation data with the relevant scholarly literature, would have brought to light CNR's preliminary publication of the excavation, thereby providing grounds either to refuse the acquisition or to request a full provenance investigation before proceeding.

Even if the acquisition had still gone ahead, the possibility to browse the cultural objects uploaded to the cloud and cross-check multiple collections would have enabled a much more rapid scholarly attribution to the same archaeological context than the decade-long process that actually unfolded, potentially initiating the restitution process years or even decades earlier.

One of the most immediate benefits of a cloud ecosystem would have been the possibility of prompt and systematic cross-referencing between the materials held by the Danish museum and those excavated scientifically by CNR researchers. This would have made it possible to identify correspondences between decontextualised museum objects and excavated materials at a much earlier stage, significantly reducing the temporal gap between discovery, scholarly recognition, and any resulting institutional or legal action.

Closely connected to this is the benefit of immediate information exchange and simplified access to thorough, structured *provenance* (history of ownership) and *provenience* (place of discovery) data, including excavation reports, preliminary publications, catalogues, and material description. A system like the Cultural Heritage Cloud would have enabled authorised users (see *infra*) to retrieve and correlate cultural material in real time, thereby strengthening provenance research and making due diligence procedures substantially more robust.

A further important benefit concerns public access, visibility, and the shared presentation of cultural heritage. Had the Cultural Heritage Cloud been operational, it could have supported simultaneous virtual exhibitions in Italy and Denmark, allowing dispersed materials to be digitally reunited and interpreted within their original archaeological and historical context. A stable transnational infrastructure preserves data and ensures continuity in public dissemination, educational use, and cross-border cultural cooperation.

A multi-actor framework for Cloud-supported anti-trafficking Governance

The following framework maps the principal professional actors whose participation in the Cloud ecosystem would be essential for anti-trafficking purposes, alongside the specific modalities of their interaction and their data access level.

- **Law Enforcement Units for Cultural Heritage Protection**

National police forces addressing crimes against cultural goods (like the Italian Carabinieri TPC, the Spanish Heritage Brigade, or the French OCBC), within their regular investigative mandates, could be granted by the Cloud governance privileged “superusers” rights within the ECCCH environment. These rights, granted upon request through a dedicated, vetted procedure, would give them access to the full complement of data and metadata uploaded to or available in the Cloud for a given investigation. Such exceptional access would be granted in accordance with national criminal law procedures and in full respect of the fundamental rights and liberties of individuals, as protected under both national and European law.

The ECCCH data are structured and mapped following the defined ontology (HDTO: WP7, Task 7.1),⁵ which ensures their interoperability with the tools leveraged by Law Enforcement Agencies (LEAs) to collect intelligence (such as the RITHMS Platform).

⁵ Hermon, S., Vassallo, V., Sielli, A., et al. (2026) *The Digital Commons (D7.1)*.

- **National Ministerial Officials for Import-Export Licences & Custom Authorities**

Officials responsible for issuing national import-export licences and managing national export platforms (like the Italian “Export Office System of the Ministry’s Directorate-General for Archaeology, Fine Arts and Landscape” - Sistema Unico di Esportazione, SUE) would have institutional access to the Cultural Heritage Cloud. When processing a licence application, officials could initiate real-time *provenance* and documentation queries against the Cloud to inform their professional evaluation about the certification release. Customs officials responsible for checking the documentation of cultural goods entering or leaving Europe would also have institutional access to the Cultural Heritage Cloud to assess the validity of the items declared description, origin, and transfer routes, and to identify potential “red flags”. For future reference, ECCCH Heritage Digital Twins identifiers may also be added by the competent authorities to the relative forms on national export platforms and/or on the EU Import Cultural Goods (ICG) and Export Cultural Goods (ECG) portals.

- **Museum curators, institutional acquisition experts and collection managers, archivists, and librarians**

For museums and public collections curators operating under the ICOM Code of Ethics for Museums (2022) or national legislation governing acquisition *due diligence*, the Cultural Heritage Cloud would provide an essential resource for pre-acquisition screening. Institutional access for museum professionals would allow for *provenance* query and object comparison, which may be even deepened upon specific authorisation of the data provider connected to the Cloud. Visual documentation (photographs, 3D models, RTI images) combined with textual data and structured metadata within the Cultural Heritage Cloud would enable curators to perform comparative typological analysis even across dispersed collections.

- **Researchers and university scholars**

The academic community plays an essential role in the attribution and contextualisation of looted objects, as the Colle del Forno case amply demonstrates. Access for researchers would be governed by standard Cultural Heritage Cloud use and authentication protocols, with additional metadata available upon reasoned request.

- **Authenticated cultural heritage professionals**

Cultural heritage experts, authenticated through their current professional credentials (like conservator-restorers, archaeologists, art historians, demoe-thno-anthropologists, physical anthropologists, experts in diagnostics, etc., working in private practice, not as academic researchers), stand at the intersection of technical expertise, scientific documentation, and ethical and legal professional obligations. Their direct contact with the cultural objects and their technical knowledge creates a positive *due diligence* obligation, for which the Cultural Heritage Cloud is ideally positioned to serve as a primary verification instrument. This integration between physical examination, semantic documentation, and cloud-based provenance verification exemplifies the ECCCH's capacity to function as an active instrument for heritage protection for a wide range of professionals working directly in the cultural heritage sector.

Conservator-restorers example: Within the ECCCH system, conservator-restorers will be able to access OCRA (Online Conservation Restoration Annotator), a web-based tool that allows work on high-resolution 3D models stored in the Cloud, annotating surfaces with spatially referenced observations such as condition mappings, material analyses, and treatment records using trusted controlled vocabularies. Once uploaded, these annotations become part of the object's Heritage Digital Twin within the Cloud environment, enabling – in the future – cross-referential queries and checks by authorised users, potentially including police, ministerial officials, and researchers. At the same time, conservator-restorers consulting an object through the platform may obtain relevant *provenance* information previously recorded on the artwork.

4.4 Guidance and recommendations for the Cloud governance in the context of illicit trafficking

The multi-actor framework described above has direct implications for the governance architecture of the ECCCH. Potentially, the Cloud can both serve as an intelligence-ready infrastructure and contribute to the fight against illicit trafficking from the civil perspective, by promoting traceability and transparent management of cultural objects.

The following recommendations are designed to maximise this potential support from the future Cloud governance in fighting illicit trafficking of cultural goods.

1st

Recommendation:

Formalise a role-based access control architecture as a first-order governance instrument

The Cultural Heritage Cloud governance should establish, at the level of its founding legal documents, at least three tiers of access roles: (i) *public* access to heritage information openly shared by the data owner; (ii) *authenticated professional and institutional* access for researchers, conservator-restorers, museum curators, ministerial and customs officials that, identified as specialised and authorised users, may then reach out to and ask data owners access to a wider range of data; and (iii) *superuser* access for designated national law enforcement units with cultural heritage mandates (like, Carabinieri TPC, OCBC, Brigada del Patrimonio) to ensure comprehensive data availability and potential interoperability with their intelligence-gathering tools, through a specific, vetted, procedure.

The access roles, during the AISBL phase, should be validated by the General Assembly with the support of ECHOES advisory bodies; whereas in the EDIC, they should be validated by the Assembly of Members with the support of the Technical Governance bodies, each within their specific remit.

Data owners may also grant other users specific/full data access directly upon request.

2nd

Recommendation

Promote the HDTO and its 'heritage provenance'-related expansion as the recommended data standard for cultural objects documentation across the Cloud

The capacity of the Cultural Heritage Cloud to function as a cross-domain 'heritage provenance' verification instrument depends on the semantic interoperability of the data it hosts. The ontological extensions introduced in WP7 (D7.1) (*HC18 Provenance Statement*, *HC19 Provenance Assessment*, and *HC20 Illicit Removal*) provide the structured, machine-readable, and legally traceable model required. The Cultural Heritage governance framework shall promote HDTO compliance for all *provenance*-related records contributed to the Cloud, while maintaining the ontology as a living standard, subject to regular review aligned with CIDOC CRM updates and with the evolving normative landscape.

This promotion can be done through eligibility criteria for new tools, or through partnerships with external partners and initiatives mentioned in Chapter 2.4 of this report.

The challenge in the transition to the AISBL and EDIC after the end of the project phase will be to clearly establish the technical governance mechanisms through which the ECCCH will promote, ensure compliance with, and encourage adherence to the HDTO.

3rd

Recommendation

Embed continuity mechanisms for anti-trafficking functions into the ECCCH's long-term institutional design

The ECCCH governance framework shall: (i) formalise the conservation and long-term accessibility of anti-trafficking relevant data (heritage *provenance* records, excavation reports, conservation reports) as a core institutional mandate in the EDIC statutes; (ii) promote the ethical use (e.g., *due diligence*) of the Cultural, particularly among museum curators, institutional acquisition experts/boards, and art market practitioners.

Conclusion

This deliverable sets out a proposed framework for the Cultural Heritage Cloud, designed to enable the transition from the current Horizon Europe funding phase toward a fully autonomous, self-governed infrastructure by 2029. The analysis presented here - drawing upon a comprehensive review of the European legal and policy landscape, a comparative assessment of available legal frameworks and an extensive series of stakeholder interviews - has led to the proposal of a two-step pathway: the establishment of an AISBL as an interim structure, followed by the creation of an EDIC as the long-term legal entity supporting the Cultural Heritage Cloud.

The governance model proposed in this report is supported by three fundamental considerations. First, the governance must combine the strategic interests of various stakeholders with the direct involvement of communities. The proposed infrastructure governance includes a dedicated Community Advisory Board that is designed to advise and provide input to the general assembly of the EDIC.

Secondly, the governance model must be evolutive and able to adapt to the rapid economic, political and technical changes happening in the global, European and national contexts. The proposition made in this deliverable is intended to serve as a starting point for negotiation. The successive phases of the legal entity creation are conceived to allow the governance architecture to grow in scope, legitimacy and complexity as the Cloud develops, and its user base expands.

The negotiation phase that is set to follow this report will need to address several key elements regarding the composition and weighting of representation in the proposed governance bodies, the funding model which is being developed within WP11,⁶ as well as the modalities of involvement of existing infrastructures and initiatives - ERICs and data spaces in particular - and the articulation between the AISBL and the EDIC.

Implementing this governance plan would entail managing at least two transition periods. The first would occur during the lifetime of the ECHOES project, as governance progressively shifts from the project to the AISBL - providing an opportunity to test and refine the governance structures and bodies before a more complex infrastructure is put in place. The second would follow June 2029, during a period of coexistence between the established AISBL and the newly created EDIC. A final stage could be envisaged, with a full transfer of responsibilities to the EDIC as the sole legal entity of the Cloud.

⁶ ECHOES Project (due in May 2029) D18.2 *ECCCH Business Plan (D18.2)*.

The thematic section on illicit trafficking of cultural heritage illustrates concretely the added value that well-designed governance can generate. By embedding flexible soft governance mechanisms alongside formal stakeholder representation, the Cloud's governance framework could enable rapid, coordinated responses to challenges that cut across institutional mandates and national jurisdictions.

The governance model proposed in this deliverable is designed as a living framework: it provides a structural starting point for stakeholder negotiation while remaining explicitly open to revision as consultations progress and the institutional landscape evolves.

Annexes

Annex 1: Recommended technical decision processes

The governance of the Cultural Heritage Cloud requires a structured decision-making framework that ensures accountability, legal compliance, consistency, and long-term sustainability. Operational, technical, legal, ethical, and user perspectives must be integrated to balance innovation with trust within the ecosystem. This framework adopts a lifecycle approach covering the main functions of system governance, including service and dataset onboarding, architectural and interoperability changes, incident and security response, performance monitoring, policy updates, and long-term sustainability planning.

It relies on a multi-layered governance structure involving an operational unit, expert technical and legal bodies, scientific and user representation groups, and a governing board responsible for strategic oversight and final decision-making. Together, these elements form an adaptive governance architecture designed to manage complexity through structured decision flows, escalation mechanisms, and continuous feedback, while maintaining system stability and responsiveness to evolving operational, regulatory, and technological requirements.

This Annex provides a recommended decision process for key activities to be carried out within the technical governance of the project, in the late project funding and AISBL phase.

Service and Dataset Onboarding Process

1. Proposal submitted

- Submitted by: ECHOES Integration Task Force
- Sent to: Operational Unit

2. Pre-screening

- Operational Unit checks completeness & alignment with roadmap (like feasibility, maturity level, documentation)

3. Parallel expert validation

- Technical Assessment Group evaluates architecture, standards, security, performance
- Legal & Ethics Group evaluates GDPR, IP, cultural rights, AI Act alignment
- Scientific and Users Group evaluates user needs, usability, community impact

4. Consolidated recommendation

- Operational Unit compiles approvals/remarks

5. Final approval

- Supervisory Board validates strategic fit and sustainability

6. Deployment & communication

- Operational Unit notifies all boards and ECHOES Integration Task Force.

Escalation

- If any board rejects, it provides suggestions, we have revision loop and then re-submission
- If conflict between Groups, it's escalated to the Supervisory Board.

Example Decisions

- Approving onboarding of a new AI-based annotation service.
- Rejecting a dataset due to unclear licensing.
- Allowing conditional onboarding (e.g. Level 1 interoperability only).

Architecture and Interoperability Change Process

Purpose

To manage changes to architecture, standards, interoperability rules, and technical frameworks in a controlled way.

Process Flow

1. Change Proposal

- Submitted by: WP6, Technical Assessment Board, Integration Task Force, or partner.
- Registered by Operational Unit.

2. Expert Review

- Technical Assessment Group evaluates feasibility and risks.
 - i. Technical impact (architecture, APIs, backward compatibility).
 - ii. Interoperability impact (L1/L2/L3 implications).
 - iii. Operational and sustainability impact.
- Scientific and user Group reviews semantic implications.
- Legal & Ethics Group reviews regulatory consequences (if applicable).

3. Decision

- Minor changes: approved by Technical Assessment Group.
- Major changes: escalated to Supervisory Board.

4. Communication and Transition

Versioning, deprecation timelines, and transition periods are communicated.

Example Decisions:

- Introducing a new mandatory interoperability requirement.
- Deprecating an API version.
- Updating authentication or AAI integration rules.
- Introducing new version of ontology.
- Adding new supported data format.

Monitoring, KPI and Performance Management Process

Purpose

To track operational health, adoption, interoperability quality, and sustainability indicators.

1. Data Collection

- Technical metrics, usage statistics, interoperability KPIs.
- Qualitative user feedback (interviews, surveys).
- Registered by Operational Unit.

2. Analysis

- Operational Unit maintains dashboards.
- Thresholds define when action is required.

3. Alert and Review

- If thresholds are exceeded, relevant boards are notified.
- Technical issues → Technical Assessment Board.
- User issues → Scientific users' group and scientific & user board.
- Strategic risks → Governing Board.

4. Action

- Corrective measures initiated.
- Possible policy, architecture, or service changes.

Example Decisions

- Prioritising performance improvements for a heavily used service.
- Phasing out underused tools.

Incident and Security Response Process

1. Incident detected

- Detection by automated systems, staff, user report
- Registered by Operational Unit in ECHOES Service Desk.

2. Immediate actions

- Technical Assessment & Scientific and User Group notified
- Technical Operations isolates systems / activates fail-safe procedures

3. Classification

- Severity Assessment by Technical Assessment Board

4. Stakeholder notifications

- Operational Unit notifies other boards and affected users
- If required Legal Group triggers GDPR notification to authorities

5. Resolution & recovery

- Technical Operations provides fix, patch, restore services

6. Post-mortem

- Technical Ops report root cause, lessons learned and reports are presented once a month to all governance bodies

Escalation

- Critical breach (security/data loss) → Supervisory Board
- Legal implications → Legal & Ethics Group
- Communications crisis → Scientific & User Group

Time targets (SLA)

- Detect < X h
- Contain < X h
- Notify stakeholders < X h (GDPR: <Xh)

Example Decisions

- Temporarily shutting down a service.
- Mandatory security update across all nodes.
- Escalation of a breach to EU authorities.

Technical Policy Definition and Update Process

Purpose

To ensure that technical governance, interoperability, security, and data policies remain current and fit for purpose.

1. Policy Proposal

- Initiated by Operational Unit, Community Advisory Board or Supervisory Board

2. Review

- Technical, legal, ethical, and user impact assessed.
- Consultation with relevant councils.

3. Approval

- Governing Board approves new or updated policies.

4. Implementation

- Transition period defined.
- Clear communication to all stakeholders.

5. Review Cycle

- Regular review (e.g. every 12–18 months).

Example Decisions

- Updating data access and licensing policy.
- Introducing AI usage guidelines.
- Revising interoperability level definitions.

Annex 2: summary of the Digital Decade key recommendations

The EU's Digital Decade Policy Programme 2030 sets a clear direction for Europe's digital transformation, aiming for secure, interoperable, and human-centred digital infrastructures and services. While the EU has established a strong regulatory foundation governing data access, sharing, interoperability, and digital public services, fully realising a Single Market for Data requires more coherent implementation across Member States.

Key obstacles include fragmented governance, uneven national readiness, insufficient harmonisation of interoperability and data standards, and limited administrative and technical capacity. Addressing these gaps is essential to unlock innovation, support cross-border digital public services, enable scientific data use, and strengthen digital sovereignty.

Key policy recommendations:

1. Reinforce coordinated governance across data, interoperability, and digital-transformation bodies to reduce fragmentation and align national roadmaps with EU-level objectives.
2. Accelerate EU-wide standardisation of metadata, APIs, semantics, and cloud-edge interoperability to support Data Spaces and digital public services.
3. Invest in capacity-building to help public administrations and research infrastructures meet interoperability, cybersecurity, and data-governance requirements.
4. Ensure systematic publication and reuse of high-value public-sector data, feeding Data Spaces and enabling cross-border services.
5. Strengthen links between sectoral Data Spaces and research infrastructures to enable science-policy interfaces and support innovation ecosystems.
6. Support trusted EU cloud and edge infrastructures, including secure, climate-neutral edge nodes and advanced computing capacities, to underpin large-scale data sharing.

Key requirements:

The Digital Decade Policy Programme 2030 sets out a comprehensive transformation agenda coordinated under DG DIGIT, requiring progress not only in digital technologies but also in innovation capacity, research integration, collaboration mechanisms, and effective governance. This transformation is closely interconnected with EU research and

innovation policy, led by the Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (DG RTD), ensuring that digital infrastructure development, data ecosystems, and emerging technologies are underpinned by scientific excellence, research infrastructures, and open science principles.

Together, these frameworks establish a shared set of requirements across infrastructure, interoperability, skills, sustainability, security, governance, and regulatory coherence, linking digital ambition with research-driven innovation and evidence-based policymaking.

Requirement Type	Description
Innovation Requirements	Innovation encompasses governance models, coordination mechanisms, and stakeholder participation — beyond technological novelty. The project establishes an inclusive participation mechanism enabling actors from policy, research, and institutional domains to engage with European digital and research initiatives (Horizon Europe, Data Spaces, EOSC-aligned services), supporting system-level innovation across the ERA.
Collaboration Requirements	Reinforced collaboration via annual national roadmaps aligned with EU targets. Multi-country projects (HPC, cloud/edge, 5G, cybersecurity, data infrastructures) rely on joint investment and shared governance, often through EDICs. Both frameworks require structured engagement with SMEs, research organisations, civil society, and regional authorities. Data Spaces and EOSC are explicitly cross-sectoral, uniting public administrations, industry, and research communities around common rules, standards, and trust frameworks.
Governance Requirements	First EU-wide digital governance framework: aligns national and EU actions, prevents fragmentation, monitors progress via shared indicators, KPIs, and DESI. DG RTD ensures coherence across Horizon Europe, ERA, and research infrastructures. All actions must align with the Declaration on Digital Rights and Principles, open science principles, and EU values (transparency, inclusion, privacy, scientific integrity). Data Spaces and research infrastructures must guarantee fair access, data sovereignty, interoperability, and trusted reuse.
Interoperability Requirements	Harmonised technical, semantic, and organisational standards are required for cross-border public services, Data Spaces, and research infrastructures. Under Horizon Europe: essential for FAIR data

	management, reuse of research outputs across disciplines, and integration of sectoral Data Spaces with EOSC. Objectives align on metadata standards, APIs, semantic models, and federated architectures across Member States and research communities.
Infrastructure & Capacity Requirements	Ambitious targets for connectivity, trusted cloud, and edge infrastructures supporting large-scale data sharing, AI applications, and advanced digital services. DG RTD requires research-grade, federated infrastructures for Horizon Europe projects, European research infrastructures, and EOSC services. Public administrations, cultural institutions, and research organisations must build institutional capacity in data governance, cybersecurity, and interoperability at scale.
Skills Requirements	Widespread digital skills required alongside advanced expertise in ICT, AI, cybersecurity, and data management. Horizon Europe supports research careers and mobility (ERA), specialised skills in data stewardship, open science, and research software, and interdisciplinary capabilities at the intersection of digital technologies and domain sciences. Projects must address both general digital skills and specialised research/innovation competencies.
Sustainability Requirements	Digital transformation must support the European Green Deal: infrastructures must be energy-efficient, climate-neutral, and sustainable by design. DG RTD emphasises sustainability across the research lifecycle — environmentally responsible infrastructures, long-term data preservation, and green innovation enabled by digital technologies.
Security & Trust Requirements	Cybersecurity is essential for critical infrastructures and public services; trust underpins all digital and research activities. Data Spaces and EOSC-aligned services must provide privacy-preserving, secure,

	and trusted conditions for data access and reuse, ensuring compliance with EU legal and ethical standards.
Monitoring & Regulatory Coherence	Continuous monitoring via DESI and common indicators; complemented by programme evaluations, ERA policy indicators, and research infrastructure assessments under DG RTD. Regulatory coherence across digital, data, and research policies is essential. Consistent implementation of the Data Governance Act, Data Act, interoperability frameworks, and open science policies ensures coordinated and sustainable evolution of Digital Decade infrastructures, Data Spaces, and research ecosystems.

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